

Tag	Number of highlights	Meta theme 1	Meta theme 2
abandoning AI tool	2	Bothered	
comparing with managers	11	Bewildered	
describing AI as fun	9	Bewitched	
describing AI solution	15	Bothered	Bewitched
describing data sharing with AI	3	Bothered	
describing problem with AI tool	65	Bothered	
describing rollout	20	Bothered	Bewildered
experiencing pressure to use AI	2	Bewildered	
reflecting on AI risk	15	Bothered	
reflecting on appraisal	13	Bewildered	
reflecting on the future	35	Bewildered	
using AI for debugging	9	Bewitched	
using AI for documentation	13	Bewitched	
using AI for explanation	13	Bewitched	
using AI for general coding	19	Bewitched	
using AI for other use cases	20	Bewitched	
using AI for refactoring	4	Bewitched	
using AI for search	14	Bewitched	
using AI for test cases	12	Bewitched	
using AI to code at home	4	Bewitched	
using AI tool for writing	6	Bewitched	
using Amazon Q	41	Bewitched	
using ChatGPT	13	Bewitched	
using Codium	24	Bewitched	
using Copilot	19	Bewitched	
using Ericsson playground	7	Bewitched	
using other AI tools	32	Bewitched	